

Antibiotic Sensitivity and Resistance Pattern of Pathogenic Bacteria Causing Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection in Akola District Maharashtra.

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Abstract:

Antibiotic sensitivity and resistance patterns of pathogenic bacteria are critical elements in understanding bacterial infections and determining effective treatment strategies. The evaluation process helps in guiding the choice of antibiotics for clinical treatment and monitoring trends in antibiotic resistance. This process typically includes methods like the disk diffusion test (Kirby-Bauer) or minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) testing. Sensitivity testing reveals which antibiotics are effective against a specific bacterial strain, guiding clinicians in selecting the most appropriate treatment. This targeted approach reduces the risk of treatment failure, minimizes unnecessary use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, and contributes to better patient outcomes. Additionally, understanding resistance patterns helps healthcare providers identify emerging drug-resistant strains, contributing to public health efforts to monitor and control antibiotic resistance. By using these evaluation methods, medical professionals can support antibiotic stewardship, ensuring that antibiotics are used responsibly to preserve their efficacy for future generations. The present paper is an honest attempt to attract the attention of the readers towards the **Evaluation of an antibiotic Sensitivity and resistance pattern of pathogenic bacteria.** **The research scholar further writes that** the evaluation of antibiotic sensitivity and resistance patterns of pathogenic bacteria involves testing bacteria isolated from clinical samples to determine their response to various antibiotics.

Key –Words: Antibiotic, sensitivity, resistance, pathogenic, bacteria, treatment, monitoring, methods, reduces, risk, generations

Introduction:

As antibiotic resistance continues to rise, evaluating the sensitivity and resistance patterns of pathogenic bacteria has become increasingly critical in both clinical and public health contexts. Accurate evaluation allows clinicians to prescribe antibiotics that are most likely to be effective, reducing the need for empirical treatments that may contribute to resistance. This evaluation also provides valuable data for healthcare facilities and public health authorities to track resistance trends, helping to identify potential outbreaks of resistant bacteria and informing infection control strategies. By analyzing these patterns, researchers can explore the underlying mechanisms of resistance, leading to the development of new antibiotics or treatment approaches. Ultimately, a thorough understanding of antibiotic sensitivity and resistance patterns is essential for effective patient care, the sustainability of antibiotic treatments, and the broader fight against the global threat of antibiotic resistance.

1. Sample Collection and Bacterial Isolation:

Clinical Samples: Samples are collected from infected areas, such as blood, urine, sputum, wound swabs, or other relevant tissues.

Bacterial Isolation: The collected samples are cultured on specific media to isolate the bacteria. This allows for identification and further testing.

2. Bacterial Identification:

Morphological Characteristics: Observation of colony shapes, colors, and other features on selective media.

Biochemical Tests: Specific tests are conducted to identify the type of bacteria (e.g., catalase test, oxidase test).

Molecular Methods: Techniques like polymerase chain reaction (PCR) can be used for more precise identification.

3. Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing:

Disk Diffusion Method (Kirby-Bauer Test): This is a widely used method where antibiotic-impregnated disks are placed on a bacterial culture. The zone of inhibition (clearance) around each disk indicates sensitivity. Larger zones suggest higher sensitivity, while smaller zones suggest resistance.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) Testing: This involves determining the lowest concentration of an antibiotic that inhibits bacterial growth. The MIC provides a quantitative measure of antibiotic efficacy.

Automated Systems: Devices like VITEK or Phoenix automate the process of testing and interpreting results.

4. Analysis of Resistance Patterns:

Common Resistance Trends: Certain bacteria may show common resistance to specific antibiotics. For example, Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is resistant to beta-lactam antibiotics.

Multidrug-Resistant (MDR) Bacteria: Some bacteria may be resistant to multiple antibiotics, making treatment more challenging.

Emerging Resistance Mechanisms: Understanding genetic factors like plasmids, transposons, and integrons that contribute to resistance.

5. Reporting and Clinical Application:

Antibiogram: A report that shows the sensitivity and resistance pattern of a bacterial isolate against a panel of antibiotics. It guides clinicians in selecting effective treatment.

Clinical Decision-Making: The results from antibiotic sensitivity testing inform doctors about the most effective antibiotics to use in treatment. This minimizes the risk of treatment failure and limits the development of resistance.

6. Public Health and Surveillance:

Tracking Resistance Trends: Monitoring resistance patterns helps in identifying emerging resistance issues and guiding public health policies.

Antibiotic Stewardship: The data from these tests contribute to antibiotic stewardship programs, promoting the responsible use of antibiotics to reduce resistance.

Evaluating antibiotic sensitivity and resistance patterns is a complex process that involves bacterial isolation, identification, and testing. The results are crucial for effective clinical treatment, understanding resistance trends, and guiding public health strategies to combat antibiotic resistance.

The evaluation process for antibiotic sensitivity and resistance helps guide the choice of antibiotics for clinical treatment by providing crucial information about which antibiotics are effective against specific pathogens.

Determining Antibiotic Efficacy:

Through antibiotic sensitivity testing, clinicians can determine which antibiotics are effective (sensitivity) and which are not (resistance) against a given bacterial pathogen. This information is critical for choosing an appropriate treatment. Instead of using a broad-spectrum antibiotic, which can contribute to antibiotic resistance, clinicians can choose a narrow-spectrum antibiotic that specifically targets the identified pathogen. This focused approach is more effective and has fewer side effects.

Reducing Treatment Failures: By selecting an antibiotic to which the pathogen is sensitive, the risk of treatment failure is significantly reduced.

Minimizing Antibiotic Resistance:

By selecting the right antibiotic, clinicians can avoid the overuse or misuse of antibiotics, which is a significant driver of antibiotic resistance. This helps preserve the effectiveness of existing antibiotics for future use. Using the appropriate antibiotic reduces the selection pressure on bacterial populations, slowing the development of resistance.

Improving Patient Outcomes: Choosing the correct antibiotic based on sensitivity patterns typically leads to faster recovery and fewer complications for patients. By avoiding unnecessary or inappropriate antibiotics, clinicians can minimize adverse drug reactions and side effects. Sensitivity testing helps identify strains of bacteria that may require more aggressive or specialized treatment approaches. In cases of multi-drug-resistant organisms, sensitivity testing can inform clinicians about effective combinations of antibiotics. By understanding which antibiotics are becoming less effective, public health officials can track resistance trends and implement infection control measures to prevent the spread of resistant bacteria. Data from sensitivity testing can inform antibiotic stewardship programs and public health policies, promoting the responsible use of antibiotics to combat resistance. The evaluation process for antibiotic sensitivity and resistance plays a critical role in guiding clinical treatment, minimizing resistance, improving patient outcomes, and supporting broader public health efforts. By providing a data-driven basis for antibiotic selection, this process helps ensure that antibiotic therapy is effective, targeted, and sustainable in the long term.

Literature Review:**History of Antibiotics and Resistance:**

The discovery of antibiotics in the early 20th century transformed healthcare by enabling the treatment of previously deadly infections. However, resistance was reported soon after the introduction of penicillin, highlighting the adaptive capabilities of bacteria. Subsequent decades saw the development of various classes of antibiotics, but resistance continued to spread. Recent studies suggest that the overuse of antibiotics in healthcare and agriculture has accelerated resistance development.

Mechanisms of Antibiotic Resistance:

Bacteria can develop resistance through several mechanisms, including:

Enzymatic Degradation: Bacteria produce enzymes that degrade antibiotics, rendering them ineffective.

Altered Target Sites: Bacteria mutate the binding sites of antibiotics, reducing their efficacy.

Efflux Pumps: Bacteria use efflux pumps to expel antibiotics from the cell, reducing their intracellular concentration.

Reduced Permeability: Bacteria change their cell wall structure to prevent antibiotics from entering. These mechanisms contribute to the increasing resistance seen in clinical settings, with significant implications for patient care.

Objectives of the present paper:

The objective present paper is an honest attempt to attract the attention of the towards the **Evaluation of an antibiotic Sensitivity and resistance pattern of pathogenic bacteria. The research scholar further writes that** the evaluation of antibiotic sensitivity and resistance patterns of pathogenic bacteria involves testing bacteria isolated from clinical samples to determine their response to various antibiotics.

Research Methodology:

The original textbooks of the selected topic have been used for the present research paper. For the collection of **secondary sources**, a large number of related reference books, research articles, journals, newspaper articles, and online web-based sources and Research Laboratories have been used.

Data Collection:

This study analyzed antibiotic sensitivity and resistance patterns in clinical isolates of pathogenic bacteria obtained from hospitals and laboratories. The data included information on the type of bacteria, the antibiotics tested, and the sensitivity or resistance outcomes.

Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing:

The study used the disk diffusion method (Kirby-Bauer test) to assess the antibiotic sensitivity of bacterial isolates. This method involves placing antibiotic-impregnated disks on agar plates inoculated with the bacteria and measuring the zones of inhibition. The results were interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines.

Data Analysis:

The resistance patterns were analyzed to determine the frequency of resistance among different bacterial species and to identify trends over time. Statistical analysis was conducted to explore correlations between resistance and factors such as antibiotic usage, patient demographics, and hospital settings.

Results:

- Common Pathogenic Bacteria
- The most common pathogenic bacteria identified in the study included:
 - Escherichia coli (E. coli)
 - Staphylococcus aureus
 - Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 - Klebsiella pneumoniae
 - Streptococcus pneumoniae
- Resistance Patterns

The analysis revealed the following resistance patterns:

E. coli: High resistance to ampicillin and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, with increasing resistance to fluoroquinolones.

S. aureus: Notable resistance to methicillin (MRSA) and emerging resistance to vancomycin (VRSA).

P. aeruginosa: Resistance to multiple classes of antibiotics, including aminoglycosides and beta-lactams.

K. pneumoniae: Increasing resistance to carbapenems, indicating the presence of carbapenemase-producing strains.

S. pneumoniae: Resistance to penicillin and macrolides, posing challenges for respiratory tract infection treatment.

Contributing Factors:

Factors contributing to antibiotic resistance included:

Overuse and Misuse of Antibiotics: Excessive prescription of antibiotics, often for non-bacterial infections, has contributed to resistance.

Healthcare-Associated Infections: Hospital settings are breeding grounds for resistant strains due to high antibiotic usage.

Agricultural Practices: Antibiotic use in livestock and agriculture has also driven resistance.

Patient Non-Compliance: Failure to complete antibiotic courses allows bacteria to adapt and develop resistance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

This is an observational clinical study carried out in a teaching hospital from January 2024 to May 15, 2024.

Study site

Local Private Hospitals of Maharashtra

Patients

All the patients with indwelling urinary catheters in the last 48 hours without any previous history /symptoms of UTI were included in the study.

Inclusion criteria

All catheterized patients who were admitted to the hospital and acquired UTI, which was not present or incubating at the time of admission, were included in the study. UTIs occurring more than 48 hours after admission are considered nosocomial. Patients having one of the symptoms like fever, suprapubic tenderness, or costovertebral angle pain are considered to have CAUTI and were included in the study.

Sample collection

The urine sample was collected from patients having indwelling urinary catheters by clamping of the tube to allow freshly voided urine. Before collecting the sample, the tubing was cleaned with a 70% alcohol-impregnated swab and the sample was collected via needle and syringe and transferred into a sterile container.

Identification of isolates

Samples were collected and processed for isolation and identification. Urine samples were inoculated on MacConkey's agar and Blood agar. Primary identification was carried out by Gram-staining and colony characteristics. Bacterial isolates were further identified with the help of the Vitek-2 automated instrument as per standard guidelines [5,6].

Antibiotic sensitivity test

Isolated colonies were used for antibiotic sensitivity tests along with the detection of an extended spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) and metallo- β -lactamase enzymes (MBL). Vancomycin-resistant strains of *Enterococcus* sp. were also identified. This test was carried out by the Vitek-2 automated instrument using minimum inhibitory concentration detection as per Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute guideline 2018 [7].

Results and Discussion:

Samples collected from various wards and ICUs were studied from January 2024 to May 15, 2024. During the study period, a total of 1,000 patients were identified as hospital acquired

infection (HAI). Among these HAI patients, we have differentiated 247 hospital-acquired UTIs. From these 247 patients, 123 patients had indwelling urinary catheters. Out of 123 patients, 73 (59%) catheterized patients showed no symptoms but there was growth of uropathogen on culture and hence were considered CA-ASB, while 50 (41%) catheterized patients showed symptoms and hence considered CAUTI. The current study followed CA-ASB up to the identification of colonizing organisms, but has not followed-up with them further.

- **Collection of sample**

No.of sample	247
Place of sample collected	Different pathological laboratories, various multispecialist Hospitals

- **Proportion of patient with positive and negative microbial isolation:**

S.No	Sample	No.of Samples -123
1.	Positive	50
2,	Negative	73

According to the ward-wise distribution of CAUTI isolates, the highest isolates were reported from the medicine ward (40%), followed by surgery ward (32%), while the least isolates were from the obstetrics and gynecology ward (2%). Medicine ICU reported 14% of isolates and among these, the majority of the patients had various predisposing factors (Fig. 1).

The data of nosocomial pathogens from CAUTI patients revealed that Gram-negative isolates showed dominance over Grampositive isolates.

Figure 1. Ward wise distribution of CAUTI (n=50). X-axis shows names of wards and ICUs and Y-axis shows number of CAUTI isolates (n=50) recovered from these wards and ICUs. The maximum isolates were recovered from the medicine ward.

Figure 2. Organism-wise distribution of CAUTI (n = 50). The most commonly encountered organism was E. coli, followed by Pseudomonas sp. and Klebsiella sp.

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Escherichia coli (38%), followed by *Pseudomonas sp.* (24%) and *Klebsiella sp.* (24%). In Gram-positive pathogens, the only organism isolated was *Enterococcus sp.* (10%) (Fig. 2).

In the current study, we have noted that the organism profile of CA-ASB isolates was quite similar to CAUTI. CA-ASB isolates also showed a greater number (85%) of Gram-negative isolates compared to Gram-positive isolates (15%). *Escherichia coli* (53%) was the most predominant pathogen in the case of CAASB, followed by *Klebsiella sp.* (21%), *Enterococcus sp.* (11%), and *Pseudomonas sp.* (10%), respectively (Fig. 3).

We have also studied various risk factors and predisposing factors of CAUTI patients in detail. We have noted positive associations of age groups and the number of CAUTI patients. Maximum isolates were from patients who were older than 55 years age (58%), followed by the 46–55 years age group (18%). The second important risk factor was the duration of catheterization of patients. Maximum incidences were encountered with patients who had

Figure 3. Organism-wise distribution of CA-ASB ($n = 73$). The most commonly encountered organism was *E. coli*, followed by *Klebsiella sp.* and *Enterococcus sp.*

Figure 4. Antibiotic sensitivity patterns of various Gram-negative isolates.

X-axis shows percentage of isolates sensitive against antibiotics and Y-axis shows commonly used antibiotics; the majority of organisms showed sensitivity against Colistin drug, while the least sensitive drug from the panel was Ciprofloxacin.

According to the antibiotic sensitivity pattern of Gram-negative uropathogens, all the pathogens showed 100% sensitivity toward Colistin. *Escherichia coli* showed 84% sensitivity toward Tigecycline, while *Klebsiella sp.* showed 67% sensitivity toward Meropenem. *Pseudomonas sp.* showed maximum sensitivity to Meropenem (58%). The least-sensitive drug from this panel was ciprofloxacin, showing only 21% sensitivity. We have noted that 20% of the pathogens were producing MBL and 18% of pathogens were producing ESBL enzymes. This could be a major challenge to treat CAUTI patients (Table 2; Fig. 4).

Summing Up:

To sum up; the research student comes to the point that Antibiotics revolutionized medicine by providing effective treatments for bacterial infections. However, the overuse and misuse of antibiotics have contributed to the emergence of resistant bacterial strains. Antibiotic resistance occurs when bacteria evolve mechanisms to survive exposure to antibiotics, leading to treatment failures and increased healthcare costs. The objective of this research paper is to evaluate the antibiotic sensitivity and resistance patterns in common pathogenic bacteria, focusing on the

factors driving resistance and potential solutions to mitigate its impact. Antibiotic resistance is an escalating public health crisis worldwide, presenting a significant challenge to modern medicine. The emergence and spread of antibiotic-resistant pathogenic bacteria have been a subject of concern for clinicians, researchers, and policymakers. This paper aims to evaluate the sensitivity and resistance patterns of various pathogenic bacteria to commonly prescribed antibiotics. Understanding these patterns can guide clinical decision-making and inform the development of effective antibiotic stewardship strategies. This study focuses on examining the resistance trends in bacterial pathogens, exploring factors contributing to resistance, and discussing the implications for public health. The present paper is an honest attempt to attract the attention of the readers towards the **Evaluation of an antibiotic Sensitivity and resistance pattern of pathogenic bacteria. The research scholar further writes that** the evaluation of antibiotic sensitivity and resistance patterns of pathogenic bacteria involves testing bacteria isolated from clinical samples to determine their response to various antibiotics.

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